

A Study of the Ogre Statues from Religious Monuments at Myauk-U

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Abstract

This paper deals with a study of ogre statues housed at religious monuments in Myauk-U. Etymologically, the word "*Bilu*" in Myanmar is derived from the *Pali* word "*Yakkha*" meaning a "ferocious cannibal". In a wider sense, it can be taken as a cruel, merciless, raw meat or fish-eating, forest-dwelling barbarian". This paper describes which parts the ogre statues erected in the religious buildings of Myauk-U played in the history of the *Sasana* and traditional chronicles. It also mentions that practice of making these statues dates back to *Daññavati* Period (4th century A.D), that it continued to flourish up to Myauk-U Period (14th century A.D), that it is also existent in the neighbouring countries of Rakhine and that it has been prevalent in Myauk-U up to the present time. The analytical study of ogre statues sheds a considerable light on the religious and cultural situations at the times of making the statues and can also reveal that the Myanmar of those days possessed a high architectural standard and the carvers of them were equipped with high expertise on making the status of ogres.

Introduction

The original word "*Bilu*" is derived from the *Pali* word "*Yakkha*" meaning "ferocious cannibal". In the cultural or religious concept, he is assumed as a sort of a merciless, raw meat-eating, forest-dwelling beast. However, unlike other types of ogres found in other parts of South-East Asia. The ogres of Mrauk-U are found to have been changed from the *Sasanapaladevas* who possess the characteristics of protection and kindness. They guard the public (or) human beings while having loving-kindness and helping perpetuate the *Sasana*. The religious buildings in Myanmar house images and mural paintings depicting 550 *Jatakas*, episodes relating to the life of the Buddha and 28 Buddhas together with their Bodhi Trees (the trees under which they got enlightenment). There are also the images of the guardian ogres of the gates and friezes with ogre-heads. The mural paintings or frescos of ogres are not discovered in the environs of Mrauk-U. Only ogre-images are used to portray the events of the life of the Buddha. Out of the images, this paper deals only with the different roles taken by the images of ogres: styles of the ogres made in the early Mrauk-U Period, their articles being held by them, their dwelling places and the aesthetics feelings of the sculpture towards the images of ogres and culture and belief reflected by them.

Background History of Ogres

The original word "*Bilu*" is the *Pali* word "*Yakkha*". It in Myanmar means ferocious flesh-eating beast. (Myanmar dictionary, 4) In the religious concept, it is taken as a merciless, raw meat-eating forest-dweller". In general, there are three types of *Bilus* such as *Lu Bilu* (human ogre), *Nat Bilu* (celestial ogre) and *Peta Bilu* (ever-hungry ogre due to his past immoral actions). Human ogres live in the forests and mountains or near lakes and ponds. The *Adanatiya Sutta* mentions that celestial ogres dwell in the abode of the *Catumaharajjka*, which is the lowest of the Six Celestial Planes, situated on the north of Mt. Meru. (*Paritata*, 83) The king of celestial ogres is *Kuvera*. *Peta Bilus* live in remote cemeteries, parched plains, deep forests and old trees.

Ogres in the Buddhist Canonical Texts

It is known according to the Buddhist canonical text that the Buddha triumphed over the celestial ogre named *Alavaka* through the weapon of his loving-kindness. Moreover, there are also some *Jatakas* of *Kuddaka Nikaya*, which include the accounts of ogres. *Apaknaka Jataka* (No. 1), *Devadhamma Jataka* (No. 6), *Nalapana Jataka* (No. 20), *Mahasilava Jataka*

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(No. 51), *Pancavuja Jataka* (No. 55), *Sagga Jataka* (No. 155), *Valahakasa Jataka* (No. 196), *Samuddavanija Jataka* (No. 466), *Mahasutasoma Jataka* (No. 537) and *Vidura Jataka* (No. 546). (Myint Swe, K, L, M, N, O, P)

Ogres in Myanmar Chronicles

The Myanmar chronicles mention the accounts of the ogress who cured brother *Culasambha* and *Mahasambhava* of the blindness ogress, May Wunna from Mt. Popa and other ogres. Myanmar Buddhists have the tradition of keeping fearful-looking, cruel-looking, mythical figures at the pagodas and temples as guardians. Among them are found figures of the ogres at the base and top of the walls of the edifices.

Ogres in Rakhine Chronicles

As the Rakhines are Buddhist, they accept the concept of existence of ogres. So they have made ogre images since *Dhannavatai* Period. (This is proved by the discovery of ogre images excavated from Maha Myatmuni Mound and its environs).

The tradition of sculpturing ogre-images had been in existence in Rakhine throughout *Dhannavati*, *Vesali*, Launggyat and Mrauk-U Period. Even today, ogre-images can be found at many religious edifices in Mrauk-U.

The Ogres during Mrauk-U Period

In the early Mrauk-U Period, two *Arahats* named *Ven. Tissa* and *Ven. Bahula* brought relics of the Buddha with them to Mrauk-U from *Majjhimadesa*. Regarding this, there is a legend that when they arrived at Mrauk-U, they stayed at Bar-bu Hill south-west of Mrauk-U. During their stay, guardian spirits of the trees and the earth promised that they would guard the Buddha's relics by manifesting themselves in the form of ogres till the end of the 5000 *Sasana* Era. Therefore, it is said that ogre-images are still found to be as guardians over the religious edifices in Mrauk-U.

Ogre-Images from Mrauk-U

Images of female and male ogres can be found in Mrauk-U. The sex can be distinguished by means of their body-structure.

Visualizing the Images of *Bilus*

As human ogres were cruel-looking cannibals, they would be glut and wide-mouthed, having a pot belly. They would have big, protruded eyes, large and pointed teeth, a big nose and a good faculty of smelling. As they are man-eating ones, they would be bigger than ordinary humans. So they would be agile and sturdy. Since they are forest-dwelling barbarians, they would be black-skinned and hairy.

They would use swords and heavy clubs. They could be visualized more clearly with their articles they used such as magic wands, headdresses, seats, vehicles, partners, entourages and residences. *Peta* ogres are of over twenty kinds. Out of the four Inferior Realms (*Apayas*), the Realm of *Petas* (even-hungry ghost) does not lie in isolation. *Petas* live in the Human Abode mangling with human beings.

The Posture of Ogres of Mrauk-U Period

The ogres of Mrauk-U are carved in the following postures.

- (1) Standing Ogre-images with the two feet putting down on the floor (in the Koe-thaung Temple) (Figure 1)
- (2) Ogre-images in a squatting position (can be found at many places) (Figure 2)

- (3) Ogre-images with one knee erecting and the other putting down on the floor.
(Figure 3)

In addition, there are also some friezes with ogre-heads discovered at the arch-entrance to the pagodas.

Figure 1. Standing Ogre-image with the two feet putting down on the floor.

Figure 2. Ogre-image in a squatting position.

Figure 3. Ogre-image with one knee erecting and the other putting down on the floor.

*Source: Field Photo

The Articles held by the Ogres

The ogres are apt to hold swords, spears, heavy clubs, etc. Some hold lotus flowers and buds. However, strangely, there are some ogress-images holding their own breasts sitting at the Shitthaung Temple and standing at the Koe-thaung Temple.

Identifying Ogres through their Posture

The ogres with tusks standing upright, holding a staff, a sword or a spear can be regarded as wild ogres. In addition, the ogres with tusks dropping downwards, holding lotus flowers can be regarded as gentle ogres or guardians of the *Sasana*.

A Prominent Place for Ogres

Yakkha Hill today located in Latkauk-Zay Ward, Mrauk-U is believed to have been a hill inhabited by ogres in ancient times. Strangely, this hill is bare of pagodas and Buddha images. (Note: There are three hills in Mrauk-U which are bare of pagodas or Buddha images.) These are:

1. Nakkha Hill

It is a considerably high hill standing to the north-east of the Shithaung Temple and west of the Yadanamanaung Pagoda in Mrauk-U. (It is said that Rakhine astrologers observed constellations in the sky from this hill in Mrauk-U Period.)

2. Rwan (or) Lun Hill

It is a low hill to the south-east of the palace-mound (today, there is a state High School near it). (This hill is so called, for it is the place where the royal drum was beaten ("Rwan" in Rakhine means "beat the drums" in Mrauk-U Period.)

3. Yakkha or Rakkha Hill

It is the hill inhabited by the guardian ogres of the city in Mrauk-U Period. It is today called Rakkha Hill.

The Ogres in South-East Asian Countries

Making ogre-images in other South-east Asian countries is much earlier than that in Myanmar. It is said that ogre-images are discovered at the 5th or 6th century AD temples in Cambodia and Thailand. The practice of making ogre images arrived in China and Indonesia in about 7th century AD and in Bangladesh in the 8th century AD. The bronze ogre-images are found in India and China.

The Architectural Standard of Ogre-Images

Architecturally, the workmanship of Bangladesh and Indonesia ogre-images is of the second class. (San Shwe, 1993, 15) The workmanship of ogre-images in Bagan of Myanmar is of the third class and that of ogre-images in Mrauk U is of the second class. The workmanship of ogre-images in Mrauk-U is neat, beautiful and can assume a fearful look as well as inspire a sense of guarding the pagoda. The ogre-image at the Koe-Thaung Temple does not assume a fearful look. But this ogre with her hands holding the breast suggests that she would guard the people as she does to her own children. As it is similar to the image of guardian goddess of the earth, it can be assumed that it is placed at the temple as a guardian.

Assessment of Ogres in Mrauk-U through Archaeology

Traditionally, images of lion, celestial serpent (nags), *Makara*, crocodile, tiger, elephant, horse, *Garula*, *Yakkha*, ogre, etc are placed as guardians at the entrances to the temples, pagodas, stupas, Buddha images, ordination halls, monasteries, pavilions, vestibules, stair-ways etc in Mrauk-U. If they are studied from the point of view of architecture, the three following basic points can be observed.

Function: Ogre-images are placed at the religious edifices with a view to perpetuating the donated buildings and giving satisfaction to the donors.

Form: The images must be made to be in proportion to the shape of the buildings. For example, the ogre-images placed in the inner corridors of the Shitthaung Temple are small and in a squatting position.

Expression: These images can convey the aesthetic feelings to the viewers. In other words, they are the feelings associated with their heavy agile, dull, active fearful and pleasant look.

The carvers have to make the images as desired by the donors. It is thought that ogre-images of Mrauk-U Period had to be carved on the basis of the thoughts, concepts, customs, and traditions of the people at that time. According to the wish of the donors and architects, the concept of the thirty one planes of existence, four continents with Mt. Meru at the centre of them, etc was conceived. It is said that *Naga*, *Garula*, *Yakkhas*, *Gandbbha* reside at Mt. Meru. (Picron, 25-27)

At the top of Mt. Meru is *Tavatimsa* over which the *Sakka* rules. Under it are the abodes of *Catumaharajika* over which the four celestial kings rule. Under them are the Human Abode and the four Inferior Realms (*Apaya*): Realm of Animals Realm of *Peta* (ever-hungry ghost), Realm of *Ausrakaya* (Demi-god) and Realm of *Niraya* (Hell). It is known through the shape and structure of the donated buildings that the donors and architects accepted the above cosmological concept of Mt. Meru and four continents.

Grotesque quality is the most important in carving the facial expression of an ogre. To be able to arouse the aesthetic feelings from the ogre-images, the carvers and sculptors put much efforts in shaping the eyes, eye-brows, mouths, lips, noses, etc for the images to bear: (1) a fearful, (2) a frightening, (3) a disgusting, (4) a compelling, (5) a detestable and (6) a loathing look.

Discussion

Ogres in relief or image can be discovered in some religious edifices belonging to Bagan Period extending between the 11th century AD and the 13th century AD. They are made of stone or wood or frescos or in mural paintings. However, the ogre-images or figures datable to Pre-Bagan Period cannot be found so far. Ogre-figures and images are found on the waist-bands of the images of *devas* placed at the gates to the temples of Bagan Period, on the waist-bands of the main pillars inside the temples, among the images depicting the lives of the Buddha, on the right and left walls of the gates to the temples, on the right and left walls of the gates to the shrine-halls, on the cornice of the exterior walls and at the top and the base of the cornice-pilasters. In most cases, ogre-images of Bagan Period can be found only to be friezes with ogre-heads with their mouths biting flowers and with their hands holding the flowers. On the other hand, the ogre-images of Mrauk-U Period are found in the whole body. They are found holding weapons rather than flowers. This suggests that they guard or protect the buildings they are placed.

The stone ogre-stature found at the Koe-Thaung Temple is a standing image and placed north of the gate to the second tunnel in the western part of the temple. It is a celestial ogre-image five feet high, three feet wide and 6 inches in thickness. The peculiarity of the image is that it is holding its right breast with its right hand. It is the image of ogress assuming a kind look, suggesting that she will guard and protect the public as her own off-springs. The statue of *Lakshmi* made in the 1st century AD and Mathura *deva* image which was exhibited at New Delhi Museum of India hold their left breasts with the left hands, assuming the gesture of bringing happiness, abundance and protection. (See Figure 4) The ogre-images of Mrauk-U are considered to bear such sense. It is found that the practice of worshipping of images first appeared in India and subsequently it spread to other countries. Moreover, it is observed that making prominent the breast of the image of guardian goddess of the earth suggests bountifulness and protection.

Figure 4. Deva image holding breast with hands
Source: From the ALBUM of Indian Sculpture

Figure 5. Ogre-image at a religious building of Mandalay (Kuthotaw Pagoda)

Figure 6. Ogre-image at a religious building of Innwa

In Myanmar, figures of ogres started to be used in Pyu Period and were used more extensively in Bagan Period. In Rakhine, these images had been sculptured in stone from *Vesali* Period (4th century AD) up to Mrauk-U Period (16th century AD). Furthermore, image of ogres are placed as guardians at the religious buildings belonging to Inwa and Konbaung Period and the present. But they are different in shape according to the idea of sculptors. Out of them, the image of Early Mrauk-U Period bears the sense of protection. (See Figures 5 and 6)

Conclusion

This paper gives a chance to study the artistic stone works of Mrauk-U Period as well as shows that the ogre statues in Mrauk-U unlike those of other regions, do not take the part of guardians but that of protectors of the religion and culture. Therefore, it can be concluded from the 16th century stone-works of Mrauk-U Period that ancient Myanmar cultural standard was very high at that time.

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